

A INFLUÊNCIA DA REGULAÇÃO AMBIENTAL NA PRODUTIVIDADE TOTAL DOS FATORES VERDE - COM BASE NA PESQUISA EMPÍRICA DE DADOS EM PAINEL DO RIO YANGTZE.

THE INFLUENCE OF ENVIRONMENTAL REGULATION ON GREEN TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY—BASED ON THE YANGTZE RIVER PANEL DATA EMPIRICAL RESEARCH

LA INFLUENCIA DE LA REGULACIÓN AMBIENTAL EN LA PRODUCTIVIDAD TOTAL DE LOS FACTORES VERDES: BASADO EN LA INVESTIGACIÓN EMPÍRICA DE DATOS DE PANEL DEL RÍO YANGTSÉ.

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Resumo: Atualmente, o problema ambiental está se tornando cada vez mais sério, e alcançar o desenvolvimento sustentável se tornou muito importante recentemente. Este artigo utilizou os dados de 106 cidades de nível de prefeitura do Cinturão Econômico do Rio Yangtze para estudar o efeito da regulação ambiental na produtividade total dos fatores verdes. Os resultados mostram que a regulação ambiental pode melhorar significativamente a PTFV. Há uma heterogeneidade significativa. Também foi encontrado que o nível de desenvolvimento econômico tem um efeito de limite.

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Palavras-chave: desenvolvimento sustentável, desenvolvimento econômico,

Abstract: At present, the environmental problem is increasingly serious, how to achieve the sustainable development has become very important recently. This paper used the data of 106 prefecture-level cities of the Yangtze River Economic Belt to study the effect of environmental regulation on green total factor productivity. The results show that environmental regulation can significantly improve the GTFP. There is significant heterogeneity. Also found that the level of economic development has a threshold effect.

Keywords: sustainable development, economic development.

Resumen: En la actualidad, el problema ambiental es cada vez más grave, y cómo lograr el desarrollo sostenible se ha vuelto muy importante recientemente. Este artículo utiliza los datos de 106 ciudades de nivel de prefectura de la Franja Económica del Río Yangtsé para estudiar el efecto de la regulación ambiental en la productividad total de los factores verdes. Los resultados muestran que la regulación ambiental puede mejorar significativamente la GTFP (Productividad Total de los Factores Verdes, por sus siglas en inglés). Se encontró una heterogeneidad significativa y también se descubrió que el nivel de desarrollo económico tiene un efecto umbral.

Palabras clave: desarrollo sostenible, desarrollo económico.

Introduction

As environmental pollution and resource depletion becomes more serious, how to realize the sustainable development becomes important in recent years. Since the reform and opening up, China's economy has developed rapidly, GDP grows from 367.8 billion yuan in 1987 to more than 114 trillion yuan in 2021, has made a remarkable achievement. 2017 the report to 19 also explicitly proposed to "promote economic development of high quality, efficiency, power, to improve total factor productivity". Therefore, how to achieve the growth of total factor productivity (GTFP) has become important for the sustainable development of green economy. So having a further study of the present situation of our GTFP and influence factors, is of great significance for our country economy.

The research hypothesis:

Generally, environmental regulation can ease pollution. On the premise of environmental regulation, it can reduce emissions of pollutants and energy consumption. In environmental regulation becomes severe cases, the product will be more clean, also can motivate enterprises to carry out technical innovation, change the original mode of production, so improve GTFP. In the long run it can lead to the profound changes of the enterprise, change production structure, which was beneficial to GTFP. So, put forward the hypothesis 1:

Hypothesis 1: The environmental regulation is conducive to the improvement of China's Yangtze River Economic Belt's GTFP.

The Yangtze River Economic Belt has three big areas, are important for economic development, but they are different. Downstream communities are one of the areas with higher economic contribution rate, have obvious advantages. The upper and middle reaches' development is relatively backward, forming the a manufacturing industrial cluster, the process will produce much pollutants. So it will lead to different effect of environmental regulation. Therefore, put forward the hypothesis 2:

Hypothesis 2: The influence of environmental regulation of the Yangtze river economic belt GTFP has a significant regional heterogeneity.

Under the environmental regulation, the higher the degree of economic development, the more rational economic structure, the more positive influence will produce on GTFP. Different regions have different features, so has different requirements on environment, the ability of environmental optimization varies. When economic levelment level is low, influenced by GDP championship, they will focus more on GDP, lacking the environmental regulation, which is not conducive to GTFP. When areas with higher level of development, in the pursuit of better environment, environmental regulation will encourage firms to develop green technology to reduce emissions Therefore, put forward the hypothesis 3:

Hypothesis 3: The level of economic development of the relation between "environmental regulation - GTFP" function is non-linear.

Material e methods

1 Model building

In order to investigate the effects of environmental regulation on GTFP, based on existing research, this paper constructs the following empirical model:

$$\ln GTFP_{it} = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \ln ER_{it} + \sum \alpha_j \text{control}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

GTFP representative Green total factor productivity, ER represents the environmental regulation, i represents prefecture-level cities along the Yangtze river Economic Belt, t represents time, control represents the other control variables, ε it represents random disturbance, accord with normal distribution with zero mean and variance.

According to above analysis, use the nonlinear panel Hansen's threshold model to test the level of economic development of the relation between "environmental regulation - GTFP" effect, thus build the model as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \ln GTFP_{it} = & \alpha_0 + \beta_1 \ln ER_{it} \times (\ln ECO \leq \gamma_1) + \\ & \beta_2 \ln ER_{it} \times (\ln ECO \leq \gamma_2) + \dots + \beta_n \ln ER_{it} \times (\ln ECO \leq \gamma_n) + \\ & \beta_{n+1} \ln ER_{it} \times (\ln ECO > \gamma_{n+1}) + \sum \alpha_j \text{control}_{it} + \varepsilon_{it} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

2 Variables

2.1 Explained variable

Green total factor productivity (GTFP). The paper base on the GTFP of 106 cities in Yangtze River Economic Belt, using SBM ML index method and MAXDEA to calculate.

Input indicators include labor input, the energy input and capital input. Labor put is employed by the total employmentt at the end of the year (ten thousand); Energy input in employed by the whole society power consumption (million kilowatt hour); Capital in employed by the capital stock. The general practice is to use the capital stock represented by capital investment, but due to the capital stock is difficult to estimate on the level of prefecture level, therefore. So draw lessons from liu Binglian scholar's practice, used fixed assets investment amount to describe capital input.

Output indicators including expected output and the unexpected output. This paper used the literature general practice, using the real GDP of the various cities to measure. Unexpected output is measured in industrial SO₂ emissions.

2.2 The core variable

Environmental regulation (ER). Based on the "three wastes" emissions as a share of GDP, to measure. The three wastes include industrial waste water, industrial sulfur dioxide and industrial soot.

2.3 The control variables

GTFP also influenced by other factors, this article selected the economic development level (ECO), import and export trade (OPEN), human capital level (HUM), industrial structure (IND), R&D strength (RD), the level of financial development(FIA), the government control (GOV) as control variable. The economic development (ECO) expressed in per capita GDP, import and export trade (OPEN) expressed in the terms of the proportion of import and export to GDP, level of human capital (HUM) expressed the proportion of number of colleges and universities to total population, industrial structure(IND) expressed the proportion of the added value of the second industry to GDP, R&D strength (RD) used patent grant, the financial development level(FIA) expressed the proportion of balance of deposits in financial institutions to GDP, the government control(GOV) expressed the proportion of local fiscal budget spending to GDP.

3 Data specification

This article selects the Yangtze River Economic Belt level panel data from 2010 to 2020. Due to the lack of data of prefecture-level cities newly established in Bijie and Tongren in 2011, so they are not included. There are total 1166 samples. Data is mainly got in Chinese city statistics yearbook, the urban statistical yearbook, taian database, EPS database, etc. Use the stata completion the interpolation method to complement the missing data. In order to eliminate influence brought by the heteroscedasticity, so take the log for each variables.

Resulted and discussion

1 All samples regression result analysis

Table 4-1 shows the regression results of the whole samples. Table 4-1 model 1-3 column used the mixed OLS, model 4-6 used the fixed effects model, model 1, 4 not conclude

the control variables, model 2, 5 joined the control variables, considering the GTFP will be affected by a period, so the model 3, 6, joined the lag issue, a lag period significantly positive suggests that GTFP is cumulative and sustainable. From the results, the estimates of environmental regulation variable coefficient is all significantly positive, which indicates that environmental regulation can significantly promote the growth of GTFP, and it also has a certain robustness. To verify the hypothesis 1.

Table 1. Full sample regression results

Variable	Model1	Model2	Model3	Model4	Model5	Model6
lnER	0.0392*** (0.00637)	0.0505*** (0.00811)	0.0577*** (0.00600)	0.161*** (0.014)	0.047*** (0.010)	0.062*** (0.009)
lnECO		-0.0862*** (0.0228)	-0.150*** (0.0179)		0.059 (0.043)	-0.021 (0.039)
lnOPEN		-0.0135* (0.00707)	-0.0110** (0.00532)		-0.035*** (0.009)	-0.023*** (0.009)
lnHUM		0.0770*** (0.00892)	0.0413*** (0.00692)		-0.022 (0.016)	-0.003 (0.014)
lnIND		-0.209*** (0.0469)	-0.191*** (0.0351)		-0.046 (0.060)	-0.019 (0.053)
lnRD		-0.0207** (0.00864)	-0.00798 (0.00660)		-0.026** (0.012)	-0.028*** (0.011)
lnFIA		-0.228*** (0.0258)	-0.211*** (0.0196)		-0.326*** (0.025)	-0.305*** (0.022)
lnGOV		-0.180*** (0.0264)	-0.254*** (0.0214)		-0.414*** (0.025)	-0.474*** (0.025)
L.lnGTFP			0.879*** (0.0260)			0.449*** (0.030)
Constant	0.144*** (0.0187)	1.130*** (0.179)	0.901*** (0.135)	0.616*** (0.056)	-0.646*** (0.240)	-0.508** (0.212)
R-squared	0.031	0.258	0.656	0.247	0.677	0.780
i.City				Yes	Yes	Yes
i.Year				Yes	Yes	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

2 Regional sample regression

Because the different regions are different in the economic development, resource endowment, industrial structure, so the overall regression may mask regional differences, so the sample is divided into the upper, middle and downstream groups to verify regional differences of environmental regulation on GTFP, as shown in table 4-2. Model 6, 7, 8, respectively the upstream, middle, downstream reaches. In table 4-2, the effects of environmental regulation on GTFP are different. The influence of the downstream is positive, but not significant. Possible reason is the downstream areas use the cumulative capital, technology and other factors to promote economic development, so the green technology is relatively advanced, environmental protection consciousness is also higher, so the coefficient of environmental regulation is positive, but is not very significant. In the upper and middle reaches, environmental protection consciousness constantly improve, with the adjustment of environmental regulation, pollution is under control. At the same time, technical level of this areas is relatively low, the strict environmental regulation may be reversed transmission enterprise reform, realizing green innovation, to play a significant role in the improvement of GTFP. To verify the hypothesis 2.

Table 2. Regional samples results

	Model6	Model7	Model8
lnER	0.027*	0.046**	0.007
	(0.016)	(0.018)	(0.016)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
_cons	0.704	-1.665***	-0.908**
	(0.427)	(0.494)	(0.397)
r2	0.554	0.855	0.458
i.City	Yes	Yes	Yes
i.Year	Yes	Yes	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

3 Robustness test

In order to prevent the occasionality, to have a robustness test. The first one is replacing GTFP with the decomposition term of EC, the second is considering the influence of time factor, eliminate the first and the end time of sample data, the third one is when calculating the environment regulation, using the proportion of industrial SO₂ emissions to GDP.

Three robustness regression is shown in table 4-3. According to the table, after taking into account the above factors, the core variable environmental regulation is significantly positive, regression results is relatively stable, the conclusion of the reliability is higher.

Table 3. Regional samples results.

	Model9	Model10	Model11
lnER	0.134***	0.021**	0.039***
	(0.011)	(0.009)	(0.008)
Controls	Yes	Yes	Yes
_cons	-0.365	-0.124	-0.681***
	(0.284)	(0.227)	(0.238)
r2	0.943	0.415	0.678
id	Yes	Yes	Yes
year	Yes	Yes	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

4 Further analysis: threshold regression

On the basis of the above regression, using the economic development as the threshold variable, considering whether there is a nonlinear relationship between the environment regulation and GTFP. The results are as follows.

From table 4-4, the double threshold model failed the test, a single threshold model passes the test, it shows that the level of economic development of the relation between "environmental regulation - GTFP" function is non-linear and has significant single threshold effect, the threshold value of 0.9397.

Threshold regression is presented in table 4-5. It can be seen from the table, when economic development level is lower than 0.9397, the estimated coefficient for the environmental regulation 0.042, significantly positive, while the economy development degree is greater than 0.9397, environmental regulation of regression coefficient is positive, coefficient

increases to 0.06, it shows that the level of economic development has a positive adjustment function for the relationship between environment regulation and the GTFP, and the marginal benefits of the nonlinear relation is increasing.

Table 4. Panel threshold estimation and significance test results

Threshold variable	The threshold number	Threshold value	P-Value	Lower limit of confidence interval	Upper limit of confidence interval	The number of BS
ECO	A single threshold	0.9397	0.000	0.9350	0.9460	300
	Double threshold	1.7018	0.667	1.5948	1.7118	300

Table 5. Threshold regression model.

Variable	lnGTFP
lnER(lnECO $\leq$ 0.9397)	0.042***
	(0.010)
LnER(lnECO $>$ 0.9397)	0.060***
	(0.010)
Controls	Yes
_cons	-0.481*
	(0.220)
i.City	Yes
i.Year	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses
*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Conclusions

This paper takes the Yangtze River Economic Belt 106 cities as the object, discusses the effect of environmental regulation on GTFP. The results shows environmental regulation can

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significantly improve GTFP, and the influence of the downstream was not significant, the influence of the upper and middle reaches are significant. The level of economic development has a positive adjustment function for the relationship between environment regulation and the GTFP, and the marginal benefits of the nonlinear relation is increasing.

The above conclusions enlighten us: First, improve the quality of openness to trade, strengthen regional cooperation. The study found that trade openness is not conducive to the GTFP, the possible reason is during the foreign trade, developed countries' environmental regulation is larger, and the Yangtze area has become a "sanctuary" of pollution intensive industries. Therefore in the process of expanding foreign trade, focus on the quality, attract high quality foreign direct investment.

Second, enhance investment in research and development, increase in infrastructure investment, relying on colleges and universities, research institutions, etc., to strengthen the key technology innovation ability, promoting R&D and technological innovation, realize the technological transformation, increase research on green-energy technology.

Third, based on local conditions, implement different environmental regulations. According to each region's conditions, formulate reasonable environmental regulation, avoid to pursue economic development instead of green, achieve coordinated development, encourage local enterprises to carry out the green technology innovation.

Fourth, optimize the industrial structure. During the process of trade openness, the area should abandon industrial pollution transfer. Government should vigorously support the emerging technology industry, eliminate low added value and high pollution enterprises, promote industrial structure upgrade. And try to reduce the proportion of high pollution and high energy consumption, so can improve environmental quality, it is beneficial for GTFP.

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Reference

- Zhou Jieqi, Liu Shenglong. Effect of environmental regulation on haze pollution: Based on the perspective of skill premium [J]. **Research and development management**, 2021 (5) : 79-93. The DOI: 10.13581 / j.carol carroll nki RDM. 20200742.
- Zhang Fan, Shi Zhenkai, Wu Ge. Digital economy and the influence of environmental regulation on green total factor productivity [J]. **Journal of social sciences in nanjing**, 2022 (6) : 12 ~ 20 + 29 DOI: 10.15937 / j.carol carroll nki issn1001-8263.2022.06.002.
- Huang Lei, Wu Chuanqing. Impact of environmental regulation on urban green development efficiency in the Yangtze River Economic Belt [J]. **Resources and environment in the Yangtze basin**, 2020,29 (5) : 1075-1085.]
- Jin Z H, Zeng Q.Impact of FDI quality on industrial green total factor productivity: based on panel data of 11 provinces and cities in the Yangtze River Economic Belt [J]. **Journal of jilin province industrial and commercial college**, 2021 ((03) : 5-14. DOI: 10.19520 / j.carol carroll nki issn1674-3288.2021.03.001. 5. Li J, Wu M.Dual environmental regulation, FDI and green total factor productivity: A case study of three major urban agglomerations in the Yangtze River Economic Belt [J]. **East China economic management**, 2022, 4 (01) : 31-41. DOI: 10.19629 / j.carol carroll nki. 34-1014 / f, 210818002.
- Xu Yingzhi, Yang Yingying, Guo Jin. Effects of environmental regulation on carbon emission reduction: An empirical analysis based on Provincial data in China [J]. **Science of science and management of science and technology**,2015,36(10):135-146.]
- Lei Yu-tao, Sun Jing-jing, Huang Zheng-xue. Urban agglomeration economy, environmental regulation and haze reduction effect: An empirical study based on three urban agglomerations in China [J]. **Macroeconomic research**, 2021 (01) : 131-149. The DOI: 10.16304 / j.carol carroll nki. 11-3952 / f2021.01.011
- Hansen B E. Threshold Effects in Non – Dynamic Panels: Estimation, Testing, and Inference [J].**Journal of Econometrics**, 1999, 93(2) : 345 – 368.
- Liu Binglian, Li Qingbin. Dynamic empirical analysis of Total factor productivity in Chinese cities: 1990-2006 -- Malmquist Index Method based on DEA Model [J]. **Nankai Economic Research**,2009(03):139-152.
- Huang Qing-hua, LIU Min, Hu Jiang-feng. Trade openness, environmental regulation and green total factor productivity: An empirical test based on the Yangtze River Economic Belt [J]. **Journal of southwest university** (natural science edition), 2021 lancet (7) : 118-129. The DOI: 10.13718 / j.carol carroll nki XDZK. 2021.07.016.
- Zhang Ling-ling, LU Miao, ZHANG Rui, Wang Zong-zhi. Study on water pollution control in The Yangtze River Economic Belt under the dual effects of economic development

Revista Verde

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and environmental regulation [J]. **Water conservancy and hydropower technology** (both in English and Chinese), 2022 does (5) : 128-136. The DOI: 10.13928 / j.carol carroll nki wrahe. 2022.05.014.

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